

Indian Strategic Economic Tactics and Emergent Challenges for the Developing Countries of the Region

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Abstract

In this paper, we examine the neighborhood especially Indian strategies for the region. The political philosophies and regional strategies related to developing economies in the region need synergy and strategically positive and constructive in nature. Their philosophy to rule and their foreign policy is different from all the other leadership. Indian Current Ruling Party seems involved in different terrorist activities, such as Gujarat attack on Muslims and the incident of the Samjhota express. Indian Current Ruling Party's begins wrongdoing on the innocent Kashmiri, its forces also use pellet guns on Kashmiri Muslims. Indian economic strategy is to invest on Chahbahar Port and wish to side stop the economic mega project of CPEC. Indian influence increased in Afghanistan against Pakistan with the boycott of SAARC conference scheduled in Pakistan. The international community has found that Indian current political leadership is as one of the most influential negative political personality among the world leaders.

Key Words: Indian Current Ruling Party's Negativity, India, Muslims, Pakistan, Indian Current Ruling Party's Relation with Neighboring Countries.

JEL Classification: O53.

Introduction

India Background

Leadership is not a name of things; it's not about a title. It's about Inspiration, influence, impact and attractive positively to other people's or audience. People who recognize that others' needs, qualities, and sentiments matter to them are often the most influential group members, while the individuals who dependably push to influence, attempt to command others and disregard the desires and assessments of others are often the least powerful members (McMillan, & Chavis, 1986). The Influence is a bidirectional thought. In one heading, there is for a section to be maneuvered into a social event, he or she ought to have some influence on what the get-together does (Peterson & Martens, 1972; Solomon, 1960; Zander & Cohen, 1955).

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Indian Current Ruling Party's Involvement

The BJP won the election of Lok Sabha in 1998, and the correct PM of India becomes the General Secretary. In 2001, that times the Chief Minister of Gujarat, Mr. Keshubhai Patel's failing health, poor management and corruption allegations, India was supplanted and selected in as the new Chief Minister of Gujarat. In 2002 election of legislative assembly Modi was elected, after that, his Chief Minister coexisted for 12 years in Gujarat.

Ahmad (2015) argues that the Hindu nationalists forced for Indian Muslims the physical and mental segment, which served Likewise a centrifugal power to southern Asian regionalism. Those strikes on people's assets, properties, equipment's, on lives, honor and furthermore, Muslims religious places and also destroying of Mosques and sending a negative message in the world, especially those Muslims living in neighboring countries. Indian Muslims mostly struggled hard to demonstrate that they were faithful Indians, but Indian Government, Indian media, as well as Indian Political parties for the most suspect them.

Indian Current Ruling Party's Tactics in India

The 2014 election battle of the BJP was different because in the history of Indian election first time a chief minister participated in the Prime Ministerial. The change the BJP's old tom in several ways. At that time, in an election campaign, India concentrated on attempted and tried strategies and themes, including rank government issues, caste politics, anti-corruption, And in India a lot of Hindu nationalist associations when and where pertinent. The RSS is a Hindu nationalist network plays an essential role, which is a customary part of the BJP. Another tactic of India was Pakistan, Indian political leadership's speech against Pakistan in Gujarat and state election. There is a connection between mental authoritarianism and political fascism, and the riots organized by authoritarian power in Gujarat have stabilized the political involvement of Authoritarian leader such as India (Jaffrelot, 2015).

Kashmir Issue

Kashmir is the defining component in Pakistan and India bilateral relations. It is not only the strategic but economic strength of Pakistan. Since 1947, after the partition of Pakistan and India, there has been a cause of crises and wars between them. Due to Kashmir defining, Pakistan-India relations have not gone ahead and Kashmir is facing problems and any good, solution, (Zulfqar, 2013). Hafeez (2016) argued that after India Government, the Kashmiri people facing the problem due to his negative policies, he begins wrongdoing on them. The assassination of Burhan Wani in July 2016, who is the one of young Kashmiri freedom fighters, which led to huge protests against the India held Kashmir, that come about in the demise of innocent protesters, as well as the use of pellet guns on the innocent Kashmiri of India forces that likewise blinded a huge number of innocent people of Kashmir.

Haider (2015) examines that after the power, India took after his predecessor's approach of holding converse with the leader of Kashmir and as well as starting the peace process with Pakistan. In opposition to the desires, Indian current Govt. tried to specifically connect with the general population of Kashmir by offering them good jobs, good administration system and development, while ignoring the disputed area, the important

dialogue with Pakistan, and the important role Kashmiri Leaders. India again postponed dialogue with Pakistan. At first, the Foreign Secretary-level dialogue was canceled by the India government in August 2014. In spite of the way that India positioned a huge number of her troops mined the entire range around the LoC, Pakistan recommended to India to give the monitoring of LoC to the UN however India declined to propose which showed that she wrongly putting allegations on Pakistan. Pakistan wants to the solution of Kashmir issue, as indicated by UN resolutions. On the Kashmir issue, Pakistan always shows her sincerity (Ganguly, 2002).

Indian Relationship with Neighboring Countries

Relationship India and Sri Lanka

India and Sri-Lanka first bi-lateral relation boycott in the 1980s when Tamil activist starts separatism in Sri-Lanka. Now India has started trying to utilize Sri Lankans for own economic strategy sake but brave Sri Lankans have understood this. The first place, Indira Gandhi's deeply involved in this clash, and India fully supports the Tamil militant group with furnishing the military train in Indian areas. Second, at the same time, the Indira Gandhi government gave her an extraordinary office to find a political response to the contention (Abraham, 2006). Now India has been interested in bi-lateral relation with Sri-Lanka due to one is the India internal political and party issues and the second one is the increase the influence of China in this region and China buildup bi-lateral relation with Sri-Lanka. Sri-Lanka had been faced many problems during the post-war such as political, economic, social as well as international relations with other countries. India is the nearest neighbor of Sri-Lanka and was involved in the civil war in Sri-Lanka throughout the last three decades (Thalpawila, 2014).

Indian Prime Minister, Mr. Modi visited Sri Lanka in March 2015 was just a gesture on political grounds. After 28 years, it was the first Prime Minister who visits Sri Lanka since 1987. Sri Lanka is the nearest neighbor of India and suffering hardships from India. The almost three-decade after a long time ago clash between the armed force of Sri Lanka and also the Tamil Association, which came to finishing in 2009. During this conflict, most of the Asian countries fully supported Govt of Sri-Lanka to act against terrorist forces (Suresh, 2015).

Relationship with India and China

In Asia, China and India are the two large countries in the South Asia region, and both countries having a conflict with each other. In 1962, India tried to fight a war with China and it occurred on the border between the two most populated countries, and this was named Sino-Indian war is also called the Sino-Indian border conflict. Then during Indian Leadership visit to China, India tried to play the culture card that in the interest of Indian's in the economic advantages; India urgently required Chinese FDI to shrivel the equalization of Balance of Payment gap with China (Silva, 2015).

Relationship with India and Bangladesh

Bangladesh has been facing problems on disputation over the water distribution with India since 1971. In 1975 the commissioning Farakka barrage, India occupies the most of the

water stream of the river Ganges to her end. Subsequently, Bangladesh has been losing a lot of farming and industrial manufacture, human health, fishing and so on, due to India diverting a major portion of water in his own reveries. Bangladesh put his big problem the United Nations General Assembly in 1993 (Swain, 1996).

Relationship with India and Pakistan

After the freedom, India never becomes a good friend or neighbors with Pakistan. Like with other neighboring countries, India has her relations, similarly here between India and Pakistan due to Indian attitude, the grisly formation of the two states and later addition of Kashmir without the goal of the Kashmiri individuals prompted enduring hostility between the two states. Pakistan and India battled three undeniable wars (1948, 1965, and 1971) and one constrained war in Kargil in 1998 on the issue of Kashmir (Khan, & Wei, 2016; Ravi, 2006). Attributable to developing misconception between Pakistan-India relations from one perspective and Pakistan-China is deepening relations, especially after the historic point China-Pakistan Economic Corridor agreement, then again, the Indian mindset appears catastrophic in the future regional sustainable peaceful environment (Jahangir and Anis, 2016). India-Pakistan clash Chinese nationals were should make attacked, such as in Balochistan, the place separatist organizations operate, directly or indirectly helped by India, this Might also create a problem between India and China (Wagner, 2016).

Isolation to Pakistan

After May 2014 in general election of India the BJP were successes and India was selected as Prime Minister. For the most part of his speech of India Prime Minister India against Pakistan. In different places, the India speech against Pakistan and tried to isolate Pakistan globally. As a non-military plan to put to stress on Pakistan or to demolish Pakistan's economy, on 9 September 1960 Pakistan-India signed the Indus Water Treaty with the collaboration of the World Bank, India additionally debilitated Pakistan with critical outcome, including the misusing Western waterway and review of IWT that were distributed in Pakistan under the IWT. India is declaring at various the Ministerial Task forces for the check the Treaty, saying, "blood and water cannot flow together" (Hafeez, 2016).

The other sensational change in this region when Uri attack was happening, and the India government suspected that terror camped across the unpredictable line of control in Kashmir, accusing finger was raised to word Pakistanis on the basis of no genuine evidence are reliable conformance. After that, Indian Prime Minister India took it negatively; he changed foreign policy completely in south Asia. He increased his influence in Afghanistan through his new policies. After Uri attack, India did fire on the line of control, which was termed as strategically strikes (Syed, 2016). The 19th SAARC summit is scheduled on 15-16 November 2016 India decided to boycott the scheduled diplomatic conference, due to it is held in Islamabad, Pakistan (Undermining Saarc, 2016).

Relationship with Iran

The construction of the Chahbahar Port, India has two aims, one is short run and second in the long run, in the short run, India means to reconstruct its oil-based association with Iran

and, in the second run, India aims to make an capable of trade way equivalent to China's silk road economic belt. Another interest of India in Iran is, which export his goods through Afghanistan to Iran (Amirthan, 2017). India main interest in Iran is increasing access to petroleum items as well as Iranian oil, And India's decrease the dependability on other countries who exporting oil such as Saudi Arabia. Mr. India visited Iran and during his visit, he announced that India would invest in the construction of Chahbahar Port. This Might be a planned move by India to counter China, which has invested in Pakistan in Gwadar Port a little more than 100 km from Chahbahar Port (Kumar, 2016).

Relationship with Afghanistan

In 1996, the Taliban appeared in the Afghanistan and 1997 they are capturing Kabul and mostly, as well as all the country in 1997. India influence in Afghanistan was limited during the Taliban rulers. After the control of the Taliban in Afghanistan, India was close his embassy in Afghanistan. During this, India supported by the Northern Alliance of Afghanistan. After the 9\11 the situation was totally changed in Afghanistan. After the attack on the World Trade Centre, in 2001 the alliance military forces attacked in Afghanistan. The Taliban power overcome in Afghanistan, and the Northern Alliance was supported to the Alliance Military forces in their war against Taliban, another Government of Northern Alliance was introduced in Kabul under Hamid Karzai. India has got an opportunity to influence in Afghanistan during the Hamid Karzai Government. India's foreign policy has different dimensions in this region. India needed to assess in the Central Asian Republics and has a long-term economic concern in Central Asia. The major influence of India in Afghanistan is trying to limit the influence of Pakistan in Afghanistan. India is involved in different terrorist activities in Pakistan, such as supporting and funding to BLA in Baluchistan, Pakistan (Mahmood, Nasir, Zubair, & Ahmed, 2016).

Indian Current Ruling Party's Relationship with the USA

At the end of September 26-30, 2014 India visited the U.S, and there was held a meeting with Obama. After a few months of 25-27 January 2015, the U.S. president Obama's visited in India. That the following visited, both sides issued a Delhi Declaration of Friendship and adopted a joint Strategic Vision for Indian Ocean Region and Asia-Pacific. On 23-28 September 2015, India again visited the U.S, a bilateral meeting was held with Obama, discussion about business, communication sector, education sector, as well as an Indian social community, including in the midst of his tour of the Silicon Valley (Kurien, 2017).

Assessment and Analysis

Indian Current Ruling Party's with Iran and Afghanistan

Iran and India alongside Afghanistan ought to quick track execution of deliberately vital trilateral trade and transit agreement that was set apart by each one of the three nations on 23rd May 2016 in Tehran during the Indian Current Ruling Party's visit. During this visit, another bilateral contact between two counties Iran and India on Chabahar port development and operations was finished between India Global Private Limited Limited (IPGPL) and Arya Bander of Iran. Indian foreign strategy destabilizes of the South Asia

region. To additionally give the military hardware to Afghanistan on the premise of helping Kabul to spare them self, India likewise builds the feeling of weakness in Pakistan and shakiness in the area. India may collaborate with Tehran to bolster fear bunches inside Afghanistan as opposed to towards Pakistan's military-political foundation and the Taliban (Akhtar & Sarkar 2015). The Indian Prime Minister's India visit to Iran (22-23 May 2016), the first in 15 years, got a deal of consideration in the Indian media. A large portion of the scope flanked upon triumphalism. The triumphalist anticipated the trilateral assignment between Afghanistan, India and Iran on Chahbahar as India's late solution to its encompassing by China and Pakistan and a response to the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) that ends at Pakistan's Gwadar port, in the area of Chahbahar. The basic critique underscored the long incubation time of foundation ventures, India's inauspicious reputation in finishing broad framework activities and China's head begin in Iran, reflected in the bigger volume of reciprocal exchange and its railroad access to Iran through Central Asia (Kumar, 2016). In this region, the CPEC project is thought to be a game changer and won't just join the Gwadar port to Xinjiang, however it will likewise lessen land separation. After the doing well, finishing of this project, it will lead Pakistan towards successfulness and help it turn out to be economically strong. The Chahbahar port is situated in Iran. It is the basis of attraction for India since this port will open a transit from India to Afghanistan, Eastern Europe, Turkey and Central Asia. India Govt wants to take benefits for this Chahbahar port, and wishes to sidestep CPEC project and Pakistan. In his last visit, the Indian prime minister India in china took up the issue and talked immovably against the CPEC going through AJK is inadmissible (Arif, 2016; (China-Pakistan Economic Corridor 'unacceptable', India tells China, 2015).

Indian Current Ruling Party's Tactics with UAE

Indian Prime Minister Narendra Damodardas Indian Current Ruling Party's visit to UAE on August 16, 2015, he assured about the protection of migrant workers. The UAE is one of the fastest growing emerging economies of the world. Organizations across the different industries in the UAE are engaged in developing and sustaining motivated workforce to effectively compete in the fiercely competitive world business environment. It is because, "motivation" – the willingness to work hard, (Thahier, Ridjal, & Risani, 2014). Singh and Sharma (2015) found that India adopted another bilateral strategy with the UAE, and there are two dimensional. At first, it is short term and the second is long term. In the first term, the association gives financial advantages to their representatives for their execution. In the long haul, businesses are more intrigued by the development of their association, since it gives them a feeling of employer stability, as when an association is developing, there are fewer odds of it eliminating the workforce

Indian Current Ruling Party's Tactics with Pakistan

It's a well-known fact that India has been supporting the separatists in Baluchistan in their fight again Pakistani military without direct giving it a chance to be known. Baloch activists have on and on surrendering to getting India's "moral" support and a delegate of Baluchistan Liberation Organization (BLO) has been living in New Delhi since 2009. Pakistan has been routinely denouncing India for utilizing its departments in Jalalabad and Kandahar to reserve, prepare and arm Baloch aggressors. 10 years back, senior authorities

of Pakistan had even claimed that 600 Baloch tribes were being prepared by India's Research and Analysis Wing (RAW) in Afghanistan to deal with explosives, design bomb impacts, and utilize advanced weapons. Pakistan Govt mostly accusing that the Indian consulate in Afghanistan is using against Pakistan and plan, train and provide funding to arm Baloch militants. A Few years back, Pakistani higher-ranking officials alleged that India agency RAW had been trained 600 Baloch tribes' in Afghanistan (Swain, 2016). In the month of March 2016 Pakistani forces arrested an Indian spy in Baluchistan. His name is Kulbhushan Yadav, he is India citizen and belongs to Mumbai city of India. In a confessional video, he disclosed that he is a commander of Indian Navy's on engineer cadre and Yadav said that 41558z is my service number. He said that in 2013 he was joined RAW, and after the joined, RAW has appointed me the assignment of instability in Balochistan and Karachi. He had already gone by Karachi undetected in 2003 and 2004 from Chahbahar. In Chahbahar he had set up his business to cover his activities. He said that worked with Baloch Student organizations and insurgents for completing his exercises. In Gwadar Hotel where Chinese were living for construction of Gwadar port, he plans to attack those (Khan, & Wei, 2016).

The largest non-nuclear bomb has dropped on April 13, 2017, in Afghanistan on an Islamic State by the US military. The GBU-43 or Massive Ordnance Air Blast (MOAB) bomb on an IS give in a complex in Nangarhar Province in Afghanistan, that order was given by the US President Donald Trump. In the history of the world first time such types of the non-nuclear bomb have been used in combat (Xinhua, 2017). It was exposed as of late that this attack in Afghanistan, Killed 15 Indians who were purportedly connected with Indian spy agency RAW. These killed Indian people had been involved and planning terrorist activities to destabilize a peaceful country Pakistan. Most of these people were connected with the RAW. That the Indian spies from RAW were working alongside Afghanistan's knowledge association National Directorate of Security (NDS) (US non-nuclear bomb in Nangarhar killed 15 Indians linked to RAW, 2017). On the 5th May 2017 in early in the morning, Afghan Border Police opened fire on the FC deployed for the security of the population census team near the Chaman Border. In this firing and attack 11, civilian citizens were martyred and 46 injured. And in this attack 4, FC Balochistan man was injured. Samoa TV reported that which Indian forces were also carrying out a fire at the Pakistani areas of the border along with the Afghan Border Police, (Eleven civilians killed in cross border firing from Afghanistan, 2017). India plays a negative role and creating a negative issue in Afghanistan against Pakistan.

Conclusion

Many researchers also discussed in the different policy on Indian Current Ruling Party's national and international level and his foreign policy. After the literature review, a thorough discussion happened on Indian Current Ruling Party's philosophy to rule, which was found to be negatively influencing the region. Indian Current Ruling Party's relationship with neighboring countries and tactics in this region are harmful. Indian Current Ruling Party's tactics against Kashmir and Indian Muslims are also very negative. It is concluded that through various means and strategies, Indian Current Ruling Party's try to increase his influence in this region.

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